

Forkhead box M1 (FOXM1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : FOXM1 is a member of the FOX family of transcription factors, with the defining feature of forkhead box, which is a sequence of 80 to 100 amino acids forming a motif (or winged helix) that binds to DNA. FOX proteins belong to a subgroup of the helix-turn-helix class of proteins. In 2010, it was assigned molecule of the year for its potential as a target for future cancer treatments. Recently, FOXM1 was observed as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of FOXM1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of FOXM1 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Forkhead box M1 (FOXM1)

A partial FKHL16 cDNA, called MPM2 reactive phosphoprotein-2 (MPP2) was isolated by Westendorf et al. [14] from bacteriophage lambda expression libraries. Proteins from phage plaques were absorbed to nitrocellulose filters, phosphorylated by M-phase kinases, and screened for MPM2 binding. They isolated partial-length cDNAs encoding two MPM2-reactive phosphoproteins 1 and 2 (MPP1 and MPP2). Leu-Thr-Pro-Leu-Lys (LTPLK) was identified as the most frequent amino acid that contained the MPM2 epitope, that bound to MPM2 after phosphorylation by M-phase kinases.

MPP-1(2) proteins, respectively, contained five(nine) sites closely related to LTPLK, including two that were common to both proteins, (F/T)TPLQ and SSP(I/S)D. Thus, they identified M-phase-specific phosphorylation sites bound by MPM2 and two M-phase phosphoproteins containing these sites.

The hepatocyte nuclear factor 3alpha (HNF-3alpha) and 3beta proteins have homology in the winged helix/fork head DNA binding domain and regulate cell-specific transcription in hepatocytes and in respiratory and intestinal epithelia. Isolating from the human colon carcinoma HT-29 cell line, Ye et al. [15] described two novel isoforms of the winged helix transcription factor family, HNF-3/fork head homolog 11-A/B (HFH-11-A/B). Their experiments showed that the HFH-11 transcription factor was expressed in embryonic mesenchymal and epithelial cells and its expression was reactivated in these adult cell types by proliferative signals or oxidative stress. In an independent research the same year, Yao et al. [16] cloned a novel winged helix factor (WIN), from the rat insulinoma cell line, INS-1. Further, they isolated human WIN cDNAs by library screening and 5'-rapid amplification of cDNA ends and their sequence analysis indicated that the carboxyl terminus of human WIN was previously isolated as a putative phosphorylation substrate, MPM2-reactive phosphoprotein 2 (MPP2; indicating that WIN may be regulated by phosphorylation).

After the identification of the winged-helix/fork head transcription factor Trident in mouse and its expression description in cycling cells, Korver et al. [17] reported the isolation and characterization of the human TRIDENT (HGMW-approved symbol FKHL16) cDNA and gene.

Forkhead box M1B (FOXM1B) expression is restricted to proliferating cells, which mediates hepatocyte entry into DNA synthesis and mitosis during liver regeneration. cDNA microarray studies have indicated that age-related defects in cellular proliferation are associated with diminished expression of the FOXM1B transcription factor. Wang et al. [18] showed that increased levels of FOXM1B in regenerating liver of old transgenic mice restored the sharp peaks in hepatocyte DNA replication and mitosis that were the hallmarks of young regenerating mouse liver. Further, it was observed that restoration of the young regenerating liver phenotype was associated with increased expression of numerous cell cycle regulatory genes that include cyclin (CCN-D1/A2/F/B1/B2), Cdc25B, and p55cdc. Their results suggested that FOXM1B controlled the transcriptional network of genes that were essential for cell division and exit from mitosis and indicated that the reduced expression of the FOXM1B transcription factor contributed to the decline in cellular proliferation observed in the aging process.

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide. Kalinichenko et al. [19] provided evidence that the FOXM1B (or FOXM1) transcription factor was essential for the development of HCC. The mechanism of resistance to HCC development was associated with nuclear accumulation of the cell cycle inhibitor p27^{Kip1} protein and reduced expression of the Cdk1-activator Cdc25B phosphatase. They further showed that the FOXM1B transcription factor was a novel inhibitory target of the p19^{ARF} tumor suppressor and a p19^{ARF} 26-44 peptide containing nine D-Arg to enhance cellular uptake of the peptide was sufficient to significantly reduce both FOXM1B transcriptional activity and FOXM1B-induced growth of U2OS cell colonies on soft agar. These results suggested that the (D-Arg)₉-p19^{ARF} 26-44 pep-

tide was a potential therapeutic inhibitor of FOXM1B function during cellular transformation.

Transcriptional induction of cell-cycle regulatory proteins ensures proper timing of subsequent cell-cycle events. Laoukili et al. [20] showed that the FOXM1 regulated expression of many such G₂-specific genes and was essential for chromosome stability. They further showed that transcriptional activation of cyclin B (CCNB) by FOXM1 was essential for timely mitotic entry, while identification of the direct target of FOXM1, i.e CENP-F, was essential for precise functioning of the mitotic spindle checkpoint.

The cell cycle is strictly ordered to ensure faithful genome duplication and chromosome segregation, where the control mechanisms establish the order by dictating when a cell transitions from one phase to the next. Much is known about the control of the G₁/S, G₂/M, and metaphase/anaphase transitions, but thus far, no control mechanism has been identified for the S/G₂ transition. Saldivar et al. [21] showed that cells transactivated the mitotic gene network as they exited the S phase through a cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (CDK1)-directed FOXM1 phosphorylation switch. It was observed that during normal DNA replication, the checkpoint kinase ataxia-telangiectasia and Rad3-related (ATR) was activated by ETAA1 to block this switch until the S phase ends. ATR inhibition prematurely activated FOXM1, thus deregulating the S/G₂ transition and led to early mitosis, underreplicated DNA, and DNA damage. Thus, ATR coupled DNA replication with mitosis and preserves genome integrity by enforcing an S/G₂ checkpoint.

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/Wnt signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the

sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [22] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [23] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [23].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang

et al. [24]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [25], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [22] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [22]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [26], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here `rbf` for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. FOXM1 related synergies

Note - FOXM1 was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of FOXM1 were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1 target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), SPC25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of FOXM1 with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t FOXM1. TK1 - FOXM1 shows high ranking of 254 (laplace), 199 (linear), 9 and 171 (jansen); BRIP1 - FOXM1 shows high ranking of 243 (laplace), 245 (linear), 111 and 134 (jansen); and HJURP - FOXM1 shows high ranking of 84, 215 (linear), 229 (rbf) and 235 (jansen), while CKS2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 87, 94, 45, 43; TPX2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 169, 63, 187, 20; TOP2A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 81, 76, 94, 217; CCNB2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 161, 105, 75, 254; CDCA5 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 257, 93, 103, 150; TROAP - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 121, 147, 152, 41; BUB1B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 197, 130, 43, 189; CENPF - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 141, 65, 165, 207; SPC25 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 149, 103, 124, 78; KIF4A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 198, 11, 78, 228; NEK2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 79, 222, 153, 2; KIF18B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 140, 235, 127, 209; and DEPDC1B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of, 59, 98, 180, 93.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – $>$ TK1 / BRIP1 / HJURP.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS FOXM1

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - FOXM1	87	94	45	43
TPX2 - FOXM1	169	63	187	20
TOP2A - FOXM1	81	76	94	217
CCNB2 - FOXM1	161	105	75	254
CDCA5 - FOXM1	257	93	103	150
TROAP - FOXM1	121	147	152	41
TK1 - FOXM1	254	199	9	171
BUB1B - FOXM1	197	130	43	189
CENPF - FOXM1	141	65	165	207
SPC25 - FOXM1	149	103	124	78
KIF4A - FOXM1	198	11	78	228
NEK2 - FOXM1	79	222	153	2
KIF18B - FOXM1	140	235	127	209
BRIP1 - FOXM1	243	245	111	134
DEPDC1B - FOXM1	59	98	180	93
HJURP - FOXM1	84	215	229	235

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t FOXM1	
TK1	FOXM1
BRIP1	FOXM
HJURP	FOXM1

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and Individual members.

3.1.2. FOXM1 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by FOXM1, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. I document here, the 2nd order combinations with FOXM1, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the FOXM1 and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, ATPase Na⁺/K⁺ transporting subunit alpha 2 (ATP1A2), MDS1 and EVI1 complex locus (MECOM), Rho GTPase activating protein 28 (ARHGAP28), dehydrogenase/reductase 2 (DHRS2), anterior gradient 2, protein disulphide isomerase family member (AGR2), solute carrier family 6 member 12 (SLC6A12), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 3 (NT5DC3), centromere protein A (CENPA), endonuclease/exonuclease/phosphatase family domain containing 1 (EPPD1), prostate transmembrane protein, androgen induced 1 (PMEPA1), H1.3 linker histone, cluster member (HIST1H1D), doublecortin like kinase 1 (DCLK1), CD101 molecule (CD101), Rap guanine nucleotide exchange factor 5 (RAPGEF5), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 39 (ARHGEF39), nucleolar and spindle associated protein 1 (NUSAP1), kinesin family member 23 (KIF23), cartilage intermediate layer protein (CILP), solute carrier family 7 member 1 (SLC7A1), ADAM metalloproteinase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 17 (ADAMTS17), denticleless E3 ubiquitin protein ligase homolog (DTL), synaptotagmin like 5 (SYTL5), cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (CDKN2A), diacylglycerol kinase iota (DGKI), thymosin beta 15A (TMSB15A), solute carrier family 13 member 3 (SLC13A3), H2B clustered histone 5 (HIST1H2BD), S100 calcium binding protein A1 (S100A1), plexin domain containing 1 (PLXDC1), SPC24 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC24), coiled-coil domain containing 78 (CCDC78), tubulin epsilon and delta complex 2 (TEDC2), melanotransferrin (MELTF), PTTG1 regulator of sister chromatid separation, securin (PTTG1), G protein-coupled receptor 146 (GPR146), maternal embryonic leucine zipper kinase (MELK), spindle and kinetochore associated complex subunit 3 (SKA3), PDZ binding kinase (PBK), establishment of sister chromatid cohesion N-acetyltransferase 2 (ESCO2), membrane associated ring-CH-type finger 3 (MARCH3), exonuclease 1 (EXO1), ETS variant transcription factor 4 (ETV4), cyclin N-terminal domain containing 1 (CNTD1), H2B clustered histone 4 (HIST1H2BC), collagen type XVIII alpha 1 chain (COL18A1), cell division cycle associated 2 (CDCA2), ERCC excision repair 6 like, spindle assembly checkpoint helicase (ERCC6L), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 4 (HACD4), FAM111 trypsin like peptidase B (FAM111B), X-ray repair cross complementing 2 (XRCC2), solute carrier family 22 member 20, pseudogene (SLC22A20P), spire type actin nucleation factor 2 (SPIRE2), tripartite motif containing 59 (TRIM59), coiled-coil domain containing 183 (CCDC183), reticulocalbin 1 pseudogene 2 (RCN1P2), PITX1 antisense RNA 1 (C5orf66), MIR181A1 host gene (MIR181A1HG), deleted in lymphocytic leukemia 2 (DLEU2) and uroplakin 3B (UPK3B), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of FOXM1 with these genes.

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of FOXM1 with these YAP-regulated genes, that were reported to

be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t FOXM1.

RANKING UNKNOWN COMPONENTS VS FOXM1									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN COMPONENTS W.R.T FOXM1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ATP1A2 - FOXM1	245	241	3	144	MECOM - FOXM1	37	133	172	244
ARHGAP28 - FOXM1	202	251	101	119	DHRS2 - FOXM1	221	242	6	147
AGR2 - FOXM1	258	239	1	125	SLC6A12 - FOXM1	246	167	29	155
NT5DC3 - FOXM1	179	202	136	82	CENPA - FOXM1	200	177	195	225
EEPDP1 - FOXM1	219	240	38	202	PMEP1 - FOXM1	227	137	164	161
HIST1H1D - FOXM1	139	41	248	195	DCLK1 - FOXM1	146	30	225	211
CD101 - FOXM1	256	132	21	168	RAPGEF5 - FOXM1	165	153	142	99
ARHGEF39 - FOXM1	75	161	162	248	NUSAP1 - FOXM1	214	131	40	229
KIF23 - FOXM1	145	131	40	229	CILP - FOXM1	237	128	15	205
SLC7A1 - FOXM1	248	231	84	198	ADAMTS17 - FOXM1	147	205	135	165
DTL - FOXM1	98	227	159	246	SYTL5 - FOXM1	153	223	167	219
CDKN2A - FOXM1	65	184	132	236	DGKI - FOXM1	176	203	146	54
TMSB15A - FOXM1	142	110	178	156	SLC13A3 - FOXM1	228	114	241	241
HIST1H2BD - FOXM1	191	68	214	173	S100A1 - FOXM1	213	212	99	201
PLXDC1 - FOXM1	192	200	7	177	SPC24 - FOXM1	189	185	22	253
CCDC78 - FOXM1	96	134	150	210	TEDC2 - FOXM1	174	187	176	27
MELTF - FOXM1	123	174	224	222	PTTG1 - FOXM1	190	208	139	249
GPR146 - FOXM1	91	237	212	174	MELK - FOXM1	159	143	216	250
SKA3 - FOXM1	252	182	171	251	PBK - FOXM1	178	214	57	256
ESCO2 - FOXM1	225	253	89	169	MARCH3 - FOXM1	206	255	88	135
EXO1 - FOXM1	253	216	192	9	ETV4 - FOXM1	122	228	173	170
CNTD1 - FOXM1	240	170	163	199	HIST1H2BC - FOXM1	128	166	168	237
COL18A1 - FOXM1	171	172	188	105	CDCA2 - FOXM1	181	207	140	128
ERCC6L - FOXM1	133	180	80	233	HACD4 - FOXM1	234	238	118	245
FAM111B - FOXM1	241	204	215	182	XRCC2 - FOXM1	215	100	129	230
SLC22A20P - FOXM1	130	229	44	226	SPIRE2 - FOXM1	182	234	158	203
TRIM59 - FOXM1	255	159	62	137	CCDC183 - FOXM1	120	175	219	239
RCN1P2 - FOXM1	188	233	143	188	C5orf66 - FOXM1	222	218	160	52
MIR181A1HG - FOXM1	143	206	256	22	DLEU2 - FOXM1	224	194	148	227
UPK3B - FOXM1	9	163	190	153					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS unknown components.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 → ATP1A2 / MECOM / ARHGAP28 / DHRS2 / AGR2 / SLC6A12 / NT5DC3 / CENPA / EEPDP1 / PMEP1 / HIST1H1D / DCLK1 / CD101 / RAPGEF5 / ARHGEF39 / NUSAP1 / KIF23 / CILP / SLC7A1 / ADAMTS17 / DTL / SYTL5 / CDKN2A / DGKI / TMSB15A / SLC13A3 / HIST1H2BD / S100A1 / PLXDC1 / SPC24 / CCDC78 / TEDC2 / MELTF / PTTG1 / GPR146 / MELK / SKA3 / PBK / ESCO2 / MARCH3 / EXO1 / ETV4 / CNTD1 / HIST1H2BC / COL18A1 / CDCA2 / ERCC6L / HACD4 / FAM111B / XRCC2 / SLC22A20P / SPIRE2 / TRIM59 / CCDC183 / RCN1P2 / C5orf66 / MIR181A1HG / DLEU2 / UPK3B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t FOXM1	
ATP1A2 / MECOM / ARHGAP28 / DHRS2 ...	
AGR2 / SLC6A12 / NT5DC3 / CENPA ...	
EEPD1 / PMEPA1 / HIST1H1D / DCLK1 ...	
CD101 / RAPGEF5 / ARHGEF39 / NUSAP1 ...	
KIF23 / CILP / SLC7A1 / ADAMTS17 / DTL ...	
SYTL5 / CDKN2A / DGKI / TMSB15A ...	
SLC13A3 / HIST1H2BD / S100A1 / PLXDC1 ...	
SPC24 / CCDC78 / TEDC2 / MELTF / PTTG1 ...	
GPR146 / MELK / SKA3 / PBK / ESCO2 ...	
MARCH3 / EXO1 / ETV4 / CNTD1 / HIST1H2BC ...	
COL18A1 / CDCA2 / ERCC6L / HACD4 / FAM111B ...	
XRCC2 / SLC22A20P / SPIRE2 / TRIM59 ...	
CCDC183 / RCN1P2 / C5orf66 / MIR181A1HG ...	
DLEU2 / UPK3B	FOXM1

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and unknown components.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic FOXM1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of FOXM1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

5. References

References

- [1] A. J. Patel, Y.-W. Wan, R. Al-Ouran, J.-P. Revelli, M. F. Cardenas, M. Oneissi, L. Xi, A. Jalali, J. F. Magnotti, D. M. Muzny, et al., Molecular profiling predicts meningioma recurrence and reveals loss of dream complex repression in aggressive tumors, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116 (2019) 21715–21726.
- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] H. N. Vasudevan, S. E. Braunstein, J. J. Phillips, M. Pekmezci, B. A. Tomlin, A. Wu, G. F. Reis, S. T. Magill, J. Zhang, F. Y. Feng, et al., Comprehensive molecular profiling identifies foxm1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation, *Cell reports* 22 (2018) 3672–3683.
- [4] D. N. Louis, A. Perry, P. Wesseling, D. J. Brat, I. A. Cree, D. Figarella-Branger, C. Hawkins, H. Ng, S. M. Pfister, G. Reifenberger, et al., The 2021 who classification of tumors of the central nervous system: a summary, *Neuro-oncology* 23 (2021) 1231–1251.
- [5] S. H. Torp, O. Solheim, A. J. Skjulsvik, The who 2021 classification of central nervous system tumours: a practical update on what neurosurgeons need to know a minireview, *Acta Neurochirurgica* 164 (2022) 2453–2464.
- [6] A. Czarnetzki, E. Schwaderer, C. M. Pusch, Fossil record of meningioma, *The Lancet* 362 (2003) 408.
- [7] D. O. Okonkwo, E. R. Laws Jr, Meningiomas: historical perspective, in: *Meningiomas*, Springer, 2009, pp. 3–10.
- [8] S. Paterniti, Meningiomas surgery in italy in the nineteenth century: Historical review, *Austin Neurosurg Open Access* 2 (2015) 1030.
- [9] Z. Pecchioli, Soria di un fungo della dura madre, operato collestirpazione dal professor zanobi pecchioli, *Nuovo Giornale de'LetteratiScienze* 36 (1838) 39–44.
- [10] H. Cushing, The meningiomas (dural endotheliomas): their source, and favoured seats of origin, *Brain* 45 (1922) 282–316.

- [11] W. contributors, Meningioma — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 2024. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Meningioma&oldid=1259055917>, online; accessed 11-April-2025.
- [12] M. N. Pamir, P. M. Black, R. Fahlbusch, Meningiomas : a comprehensive text, Elsevier Health Sciences, 2010.
- [13] F. Szulzewsky, H. N. Thirimanne, E. C. Holland, Meningioma: current updates on genetics, classification, and mouse modeling, *Upsala Journal of Medical Sciences* 129 (2024) 10–48101.
- [14] J. M. Westendorf, P. N. Rao, L. Gerace, Cloning of cdnas for m-phase phosphoproteins recognized by the mpm2 monoclonal antibody and determination of the phosphorylated epitope., *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 91 (1994) 714–718.
- [15] H. Ye, T. F. Kelly, U. Samadani, L. Lim, S. Rubio, D. G. Overdier, K. A. Roebuck, R. H. Costa, Hepatocyte nuclear factor 3/fork head homolog 11 is expressed in proliferating epithelial and mesenchymal cells of embryonic and adult tissues, *Molecular and cellular biology* 17 (1997) 1626–1641.
- [16] K.-M. Yao, M. Sha, Z. Lu, G. G. Wong, Molecular analysis of a novel winged helix protein, win: expression pattern, dna binding property, and alternative splicing within the dna binding domain, *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 272 (1997) 19827–19836.
- [17] W. Korver, J. Roose, K. Heinen, D. O. Weghuis, D. de Bruijn, A. G. van Kessel, H. Clevers, The human trident/hfh-11/fkhl16 gene: structure, localization, and promoter characterization, *Genomics* 46 (1997) 435–442.
- [18] X. Wang, E. Quail, N.-J. Hung, Y. Tan, H. Ye, R. H. Costa, Increased levels of forkhead box m1b transcription factor in transgenic mouse hepatocytes prevent age-related proliferation defects in regenerating liver, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 98 (2001) 11468–11473.
- [19] V. V. Kalinichenko, M. L. Major, X. Wang, V. Petrovic, J. Kuechle, H. M. Yoder, M. B. Dennewitz, B. Shin, A. Datta, P. Raychaudhuri, et al., Foxm1b transcription factor is essential for development of hepatocellular carcinomas and is negatively regulated by the p19arf tumor suppressor, *Genes & development* 18 (2004) 830–850.
- [20] J. Laoukili, M. R. Kooistra, A. Brás, J. Kauw, R. M. Kerkhoven, A. Morrison, H. Clevers, R. H. Medema, Foxm1 is required for execution of the mitotic programme and chromosome stability, *Nature cell biology* 7 (2005) 126–136.
- [21] J. C. Saldivar, S. Hamperl, M. J. Bocek, M. Chung, T. E. Bass, F. Cisneros-Soberanis, K. Samejima, L. Xie, J. R. Paulson, W. C. Earnshaw, et al., An intrinsic s/g2 checkpoint enforced by atr, *Science* 361 (2018) 806–810.

- [22] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [23] G. Pujol, B. Iooss, A. Janon, K. Boumhaout, S. Da Veiga, J. Fruth, L. Gilquin, J. Guillaume, L. Le Gratiet, P. Lemaitre, et al., Sensitivity: global sensitivity analysis of model outputs, R package version 1 (2017).
- [24] H. Huang, Y. Liu, M. Yuan, J. Marron, Statistical significance of clustering using soft thresholding, *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* 24 (2015) 975–993.
- [25] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [26] R. C. Team, R language definition, Vienna, Austria: R foundation for statistical computing 3 (2000) 116.